

THE SHACKS OF RACISM STILL IN SUBJECTING THE BLACK PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to discuss the contribution of literary reading to the understanding of history. The book *O sol da Liberdade* by Giselda Laporta Nicolelis, whose plot presents the history of eight generations of an African family, since the loss of a dispute in Africa in which the sovereign of the tribe and patriarch of the family commits suicide and his son, the prince is sent as a slave to Brazil, until 1985, when the reader meets the great-granddaughter of King Momo. While, generation after generation, the narrator uncovers the soul of each character, the reader follows the history of Brazil, marked by inequality, oppression, and racism. We highlight here the course of the legislative process, from the Free Womb Law to Law 10639/03.

Keywords: History. racism. Literature. Resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Reading is indisputably essential for human beings to understand the world around them and interact with it. Thus, contributing in a significant way so that students become reading subjects is the teacher's role. Believing in this idea, the literary work of Giselda Laporta Nicolelis, *O sol da Liberdade* , served as a motto for an interdisciplinary work in the eighth years of elementary school at the Instituto Municipal de Ensino Assis Brasil (IMEAB).

The choice of this work is due to the fact that the black population is, as a rule, flogged on a daily basis even though whipping was prohibited with the abolition of slavery. Acts of racism become headlines in the most varied media, in a country whose main characteristic is

miscegenation. And what better place than the school to discuss this issue, which is of interest to society as a whole.

The Black Movement, over the years, has seen positive results in its struggle and a significant result was the implementation of law 10.639/03, bringing the study of Afro-Brazilian history and culture to the school curriculum. Based on this context, the present work aims to address the relationship between the literary work **O sol da Liberdade** and ethnic-racial issues, mainly identity issues.

Therefore, the theoretical perspective of this text is based on the ideas of Carneiro (1993), Durans (2021) and Munanga (2015). This is a qualitative research, bibliographic in nature, in order to analyze the literary work in question, whose plot tells the trajectory of a people who had an invaluable contribution to the formation of Brazilian society, the black people. Consequently, the narrative, which brings a more sensitive view, also awakens the student's curiosity for the history of Brazil. Added to this is the fact that students, when reading a literary work, find a world full of novelties that often differ from their culture. And that makes them use their subjectivity to understand the plot.

Durans (2021, p.88) declares that in the field of science, racial differences gained status in the 19th century in Europe, arriving in Brazil with delays, but that they were welcomed with enthusiasm by the intellectuals of the time. Scientific racism or racialism lasted for more than a century, using arguments to justify the superiority of some human groups and peoples. These theories sought ways to scientificize economic domination.

Carneiro (1993, p.17) states that racism involves ideas and doctrinal construction, in addition to facts and attitudes. In this understanding, one can observe a founding feature of racial theories, the need to prove the existence of a superior and an inferior race. He also declares that the genesis of racism is not scientific and that people are not born racist, but that it is based on economic and social relations. It is configured in policies as a way to justify inequalities, concealing the true interests that are economic and political exploitation.

1. Literature and the struggle for social justice

Literature has the ability to take the reader by the hand and lead him through the paths of History. In this case, history goes back to 1825, a time when the slave trade was in evidence. And the plot of **O sol da Liberdade**, by Giselda Laporta Nicolelis, features a Yoruba king and his son, the heir to the throne, Ajahi. People who had their destiny crossed by the opportunistic European who saw the war between African tribes as a lucrative way to earn a living.

Then begins the greatest struggle of Ajahi's life, the fight for freedom. His unbreakable spirit stands firm in the face of the humiliations suffered. In his mind the voice of his father, the Yoruba king Namonim, who had pierced his chest with his own spear to die like a sovereign, echoes “- A Yoruba does not surrender on the battlefield... a Yoruba will never be a slave to anyone... free born... free will die...” (p.12)

Like the heir to a distant throne, many other enslaved Africans believe that freedom can be regained through struggle. Based on this belief, history recorded the Malês Revolt. The author herself, Giselda Laporta Nicolelis, brings to the narrative some of the names of the leaders of the Malês Revolt, such as Licutan, Sule, Manuel Calafate, Sanim, in order to illustrate the daily struggle faced by Africans, who, even in greater numbers, subjected to the humiliations of slavery

...nago mostly, tall and handsome black people, called malês because they are all muslims, speaking and writing in arabic and sometimes - what an irony! -, much more literate than their own masters. They do not mix with non-Muslims - they were converted by the ussás, in Brazil - and are even viewed with distrust by other slaves. The Islamic religion does not provide for slavery among its followers. (NICOLELIS, 2004, p.17)

The suffering they went through was able to unite them, Muslims and non-Muslims, in favor of the same objective. It was like this in 1835 and it continues today, with the Black Movement, which gradually awakens a collective conscience in an attempt to make the excluded stop being a mass of maneuvers. Even though the Malês Revolt was just another utopian dream, whose rebels, the vast majority of whom were killed or punished to serve as an example, left their message that the enslaved were not satisfied with the way they were treated and that they knew organize and fight against the social organization of which they were forced to be a part. As for this revolt, Durans points out that it

It was a political movement that opposed the government, revealing a process of class struggle, while at the same time demystifying the idea that there was no organization of blacks in the country. On the other hand, it aims to reaffirm the position that the issue of blacks in the country resides in the fight against racial oppression articulated against capital, which combines anti-racism and class struggle. (DURANS, 2021, p.177)

Among the dead rebels is Ajahí, the Yoruba warrior. But this story is far from over, as his wife, Gangara, eight months pregnant, flees to a quilombo in search of refuge to give birth to King Namonim's grandson.

It is in this atmosphere of terror that there, in the Quilombo do Urubu, on the outskirts of Salvador, on a misty dawn, a month later, the son of Gangara and Ajahi is born... slaves or freed...

The boy is named Uesu. He is the grandson of a Yoruba king, the son of a warrior who paid for his dream of freedom with his life... and he is born free, while the birds wake up, in the middle of the forest. (NICOLELIS, 2004, p.41)

By bringing the Quilombo do Urubu to the plot, Giselda Laporta Nicolelis once again puts the reader in touch with reality, as this Quilombo, with its vast territorial extension, sheltered for many years those who needed protection. Regarding the organization that was observed in the quilombo, Durans can be cited to exemplify the idea that

a group of individuals, when they become aware of themselves for themselves, maintain collective ties; this is an aspect of the formation and historicity of social class. The process is initially carried out when it is just an object in the social structure and evolves, acquiring awareness, self-asserting itself, becoming independent, creating values that oppose the dominant ones and the system that oppresses it, reflecting the interests of its collectivity, seeking ways to of organization for its economic, social and cultural survival. (DURANS, 2021, p.170-171)

As the reader follows the adventures and misadventures of the Yoruba king's descendants, he discovers the cruel effects of Brazilian laws. And he makes them his own reading in an attempt to understand how the legislature worked on behalf of the few who held economic power at the time. Like the law that determined the loss of the Charter of Manumission, if the freed slave spilled his former master. But, the irony of it is in the fact that proof of defamation was not necessary, the word of the said slave owner was enough. It should be noted that this situation fueled the thirst for justice that cradled the Malês Revolt, since in addition to being slaves again, blacks were subjected to extreme punishments, among them, flogging in public squares was the most common.

Time passed and in order to control the Africans who were still enslaved in Brazil and, at the same time, appease the abolitionist movements that were gaining strength, some laws were created. As for them, Durans points out that

It was no coincidence that the abolitionist process in the country lasted for over a century, going through stages until it was officially extinguished in 1888. These stages range from international pressure: treaties against trafficking in agreement with England; inspection of Brazilian territory by English ships; protection agreement and political asylum of the royal family in Brazil; unfulfilled pact with the participation of enslaved people in the war in Paraguay in exchange for manumission, in addition to the slow process of abolition that took place through legislation - the Free Womb Law (1871), the Sexagenarian Law and, finally, the Golden Law, in 1888 (DURANS, 2021, p.73)

In the book, time also passes. The year is 1883, and Uesu is called Roque, a Christian name. Another attempt to mitigate the revolutionary spirit of Africans, belittling their beliefs and religion. And Uesu, who had been born free, in the quilombo, at the age of twenty was caught in a warehouse robbery and sold as a slave. He lives enslaved on a white man's tobacco farm that he saved from a snakebite. For this reason, he has certain privileges, but remains a slave, waiting for abolition to go in search of his son who was born after the enactment of the Free Womb Law and was kidnapped by a slave smuggler.

With an impressive creative dexterity, the author unravels between the lines of Brazilian laws.

- In 1871 we had the Free Womb Law, the Rio Branco Law. All unborn children became free men, and children up to 12 years old cannot be separated from their mothers, although up to 21 years old they still remain under the guardianship of their master. So, men like Alaor steal children and sell them as “motherless children”. This in smuggling [...]
- The Rio Branco Law wanted to stimulate the slave birth rate. So, for each child who reaches the age of 8, the owner has a remuneration corresponding to the value of an adult slave. An excellent thing in terms of business. So, the children who survive are also targets of these smugglers, also because they are the strongest, of course. (NICOLELIS, 2004, p. 51-52)

The Saraiva Cotegipe law or Sexagenarian Law is another move that privileges slave owners, since the master who granted the Letter of Manumission to the slave who turned 60 would receive compensation. The justification is based on the fact that the person was losing his manpower. Not for a moment is the slave considered as a person who has been exploited all his life and deserves to live out his last years enjoying a deserved rest. Quite the contrary, even manumitted, the slave was tied to his owner for a few years, according to the law, for three years. During that period he still had to render services to the one who had exploited and humiliated him while he still had strength and vigor for hard work.

And the long-awaited 13th of May 1888 arrives, the day of the abolition of slavery. But when the euphoria of freedom passes, what remains for the slaves, then freed? No possessions, no job, no direction. Taxed as vagabonds, they become scum. And the old masters who had bet on Italian immigration to supply the workforce lost with the abolition, continue to dictate the Brazilian rules and laws. And even more satisfied, because the time had come to get rid of the black people and bet on a white nation.

At this point in the narrative, the reader meets Aliara, Namonim's great-grandson, renamed José. He works on a coffee farm in the state of São Paulo. But will he learn his story from his father's mouth? No. Uesu had died before finding his son. Abolition will catch up with

him too old for this adventure. But as a result of fate and the author's crafty inventiveness, the nephew of Uesu's owner marries Aliara's former owner and thus, the smuggled slave's past becomes clear.

Analyzing the historical period comprising abolition and post-abolition, it can be seen that significant changes have occurred, especially from the 1950s onwards, when issues of race relations came to be understood as a factor of social equalization in which blacks could be included in society naturally and without any interpellation from the State. That is, the State and the bourgeoisie are not responsible for the centuries of slavery and it is up to the blacks to make the effort, the fight for their survival in a society that has become competitive and liberal. Durans corroborates this conjecture by emphasizing that

Blacks, who were described as slaves, animals, passive, uncultured and backward during slavery, are now seen in the post-abolition period as loafers, rascals and possessors of cordial attitudes. The change in this characterization is the result of the ideology of racial democracy that preached the non-existence of racism in the country. And here opportunities are offered to everyone, without distinction. Now, in a country that offers equal opportunities, the fault ends up being the individual himself. From this characterization derive paternalistic and welfare visions and proposals for blacks, seen as unfortunate. (DURANS, 2021, p.25)

And the saga of African royal descent continues. The plot reaches 1985. Through a circular story, there is again a king in the family of Namonim. It's King Momo, Carlos, Aliara's youngest son. Very happy with her red satin mantle and golden brass crown, she will captivate the reader by revealing another face of Brazilian History.

Carlão, as he is known in the samba circles, at the age of eighty, relives his past and begins this narrative by recalling his son who, at eighteen, was called up for compulsory military service, to form, along with many other blacks, the first echelon that would to war. And like so many other young people, he dies on the battlefield, leaving his girlfriend pregnant, here in Brazil.

Carlão raises his granddaughter, Lázara. But the warrior spirit of the Yoruba still lives on in their descendants. Lázara went to work in a weaving factory and became a union leader among her companions. To speak of social justice during a dictatorship was to sign a death sentence. And that's what happened to the young black woman, she was taken in for questioning and never heard from again.

Carlão was left with his great-granddaughter, Elisângela. Communications student, who is looking forward to turning 21 and being able to vote. Exercise your citizenship in a country that won democracy after 21 years of dictatorship. But she has an arduous task to finish this

story, to reach the slum where her great-grandfather lives, who died in his sleep, and to make the necessary referrals. Since that same day, April 22, 1985, Tancredo, the depository of the hopes of the Brazilian people, died. Who would remember a black Momo king, dead, alone in his room in the middle of the slum. After all, that's what was left for the black population, the slums, underemployment, exclusion.

2. The teacher's role as an agent of social transformation

To be a teacher today is to compete for a space in the hearts and minds of young students. The Covid 19 pandemic unveiled a world of weaknesses with which many of the professors were not familiar. So, it is necessary to find ways to bring literature to the student and convince him to enter this magical and, at the same time, so complex world that is literary reading and its relationship with reality.

In an attempt to make reading a habit among the students, mainly the students who attended the four classes of the eighth year of IMEAB, the teachers of the curricular components of Portuguese Language, English Language, Religious Education and Art planned an interdisciplinary work based on the work by Giselda Laporta Nicoletis, **The Sun of Liberty**. The reading was done by the Portuguese Language and Religious Education teachers, one chapter per class. And it was up to the students to record what had happened in the story, as well as the post-reading discussions, mediated by the reading teacher. Chapter by chapter the plot was analyzed and the History of Brazil and the enslaved Africans understood by questioning young people, full of doubts and curiosity.

In Art classes, emphasis was placed on African culture, with special emphasis on African masks. The activities of this study addressed the influence of African culture in the formation of the European Vanguard called Cubism.

The Portuguese Language discipline deepened the study of textual genres such as news, short stories, chronicles, poems, opinion articles and comics, all addressing themes listed from reading the book. The coloring of the comics decorated the walls of the school's lobby during the month of November, sharing the space with the African masks produced in Art classes. This is because one of the activities was to re-read the literary work by making a comic book. In this activity, each chapter was illustrated on an A3 sheet.

In the English language, the construction of meaning and sharing of reading was thought for later discussion of the themes addressed in the poems *I, Too* and *"Negro"* by Langston Hughes (1902-1967) and in the song *"Black Or White"* by Michael Jackson. In this, it was

possible to deepen the question of the construction of the lexical repertoire of music in terms of racism, since the song deals with this theme. Also, in a cinema session at school, the film ``Harriet - O Caminho para a Liberdade was watched `` and based on it, the biographical file of Harriet Tubman, an American activist who was born enslaved and fought for the freedom of black people, was elaborated.

The film "Harriet" enabled a comparative analysis of the female characters in the work " **The Sun of Liberty** " and the female figures presented in the cinematographic work. These discussions led the students to look for female figures who currently stand out in the fight against the racism.

During one quarter, both written and artistic production activities focused on the historical events that permeated the lives of the characters in **O sol da Liberdade** . Students were able to develop active listening and took sides in relation to this or that character, demonstrating that more than following the story, they understood it and established relationships between fiction and reality.

To close the work, the students were divided into groups to prepare a seminar. To this end, they carried out the research, prepared an article in which they were guided by the Portuguese and English language teachers, organized the presentations in slides and on pre-defined dates the groups presented their work to each other. And finally, returning to one of the themes presented at the seminar, which was African culture, rice pudding was served at the fraternization that ended a long and productive work.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The centuries of inequalities to which blacks were subjected will not be minimized with paternalistic actions. It is necessary to develop in each one the consciousness of the EU, to understand and accept oneself as a subject of a nation that insists on not recognizing racism. For this reason, it is up to the school to discuss these racial issues in order to understand the value of public policies aimed at social equalization. In this sense, according to Munanga (2015, p. 29) "Laws 10,639/03 and 11,645/08/ are configured as a correction of the forgetfulness of the positive memory of slavery in the history of Brazil."

Knowing History through literature is a way for students to reflect on reality and, consequently, analyze the society in which they are inserted. Both literary work and History are full of characters, events and conflicts, they have a plot that unfolds and allows us to glimpse the best and worst of human beings. Allied to this is the fact that reading contributes to the

cognitive development and critical thinking, so necessary for young people, and we have education as the driving force behind social transformation. For Munanga, it is clear that the solution to the fight against racism and the search for equality

it does not lie in the eradication of race and the processes of construction of racial identity, but in an education and socialization that emphasize the coexistence or egalitarian coexistence of differences and particular identities. Seen from this perspective, I think that implementing affirmative action policies not only in the higher education system, but in all sectors of national life where blacks are excluded... (MUNNANGA, 2015, p. 25)

The way out of social anonymity, of indigence, is through education. Literature gives voice to the excluded and this voice needs to echo through the school, leave the pages of books and become a resilient force. It is necessary to fight, to participate in society, to support movements that fight for equality. And these actions do not happen in a burst of lucidity, they are developed and fed gradually, from the moment a student is taught to read until the moment when he becomes capable of reading the world for himself and understanding that he was educated to transform it. it.

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